

Waste Management at Events

**Frederik C. V. Hansen, Jonathan Rasmussen, Camilla A. Hansen,
Marie S. Berggreen, Andreas Nørballe, Mikkel Seibæk and Heida G. Nolsøe**

DTU Mechanical Technology, Technical University of Denmark

Due to the increasing popularity of parties, celebrations and events in the streets of numerous cities around the world, there is a rapidly growing challenge in regards to the amount of thrown waste into these public environments. On the basis of this problem, the ambition of our project is to develop a solution for waste handling at events. As a green solution, *DropBucket* is able to keep the environment clean, as well as the surrounding areas by offering efficient and environmentally justifiable waste management.

In depth research, field studies and sociotechnical analysis reveals that the absence of easily accessible and appealing disposal options, is a key factor in the progression of the above-stated problem. Every year, extensive resources are devoted to waste management at events. These are often considered time-consuming and expensive due to the amount of cleanup and comprehensive logistical work, required during the process of waste disposal from the street.

Figure 1 Deployment and Disposal

DropBucket was originally intended and developed for use at events in the streets of Copenhagen Inner City. However, by virtue of its simple design, the solution is easily implemented at events of a similar nature around the world. The concept of *DropBucket* is based around a foldable bin, consisting of a collapsed cardboard structure that unfolds to a pyramid shaped structure when it is deployed. This way, *DropBucket* ensures a rapid and efficient implementation in large numbers, during times when the need for waste handling exceeds the capacity of stationary bins.

In its current state, *DropBucket* is punched from one piece of corrugated cardboard featuring a water resistant liner and thus designed as an inexpensive disposable bin which can be compressed on site and properly deposited after use. Further developments will be based on field testings of new prototypes where special consideration is given to the choice of cardboard type and liner. The key elements of focus will be around strength, stability and environmental footprint.

The fact that *DropBucket* is not emptied after use and is disposed in a compressed state – thus minimizing transportation and emission of greenhouse gasses associated – underlines the profile of this product being a truly green solution.